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CORRELATION AND SIGNIFICANCE OF Dup A, Ice A AND Hom B GENES OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI AND OTHER CONFOUNDING FACTORS IN PAKISTAN HELICOBACTER PYLORIISOLATES WITH GASTRODUODENAL DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: To establish PCR based detection assays for dup A, ice A, hom B genes of H. Pylori and detect the presence of these genes in Pakistani H. Pylori isolates, and to examine other confounding factors beside dup A, ice A, hom B such as age, gender, diet and lifestyle characteristics with association of H. Pylori-related diseases
METHODOLOGY: This cross-sectional analytical study was conducted at gastroenterology Department, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore and molecular techniques were performed in Centre of Excellence and Molecular Biology, University of Punjab, Lahore, with duration of two years. All the cases with symptomatic dyspeptic patients either gender and with age more than 18 years were included in the study. All the subjected patients were undergone to endoscopic examination. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy was carried out and specimens were obtained for the gastric biopsy. Specimens were inoculated in the CLO or rapid urease test gel and rest were stored in eppendorf tubes containing normal saline at -20C until DNA extraction. DNA was extracted of the H-pylori by using Genra DNA extraction Kit (Life Technologies, USA) according to instructions given in protocol of the kit for Qualitative PCR detection of DNA of H. Pylori. The PCT primers sets were designed for the specific detection of dup A, ice A and hom B gene of H. Pylori using primer 3 software. The designed PCR primer sets specific for the H. Pylori dup A, ice A and hom B genes were used for PCR amplification. PCR was performed for the amplification of dup A, ice A and hom B genes. The desired genes were quantified using Real-time PCR. The PCR bands of the amplified genes were gel eluted and were stored at minus 20 degree C till to be used for sequence analysis. **RESULTS:** Mean age of the cases was found 41.22±8.04 years. Male were more affected 118 (60.2%) as compare to female 78(39.8%). Epigastric discomfort was found in the 196(100%)of the cases where as Bloating and Belching cases were noted as 180(91.8%) while Nausea & vomiting cases as observed as 138(70.4%). The life style distribution exhibited that Hand wash 188(95.9%)was observed most frequent in all cases and exercise 36(18.4%) of cases, however municipality source water was more common following by Fresh water 48(24.5%) and Filtered water as 4(2.0%) of cases. As indicated by this study CLO/rapid urease test as well as Polymerase chain reaction quantity was noticeably 100% positive in all cases. As per H.pylori genes distribution Hom B was the most common 76(38.8%). A significant association was found in the gene distribution of the H. pylori among both genders male were more linked to Dup A, while female were mostly associated with Ice A and Hom A genes, P-value 0.001. Different type of diets is significantly associated with h pylori genes P value 0.001. Water bad sources were highly associated with h pylori genes as genes were mostly found in municipality water as compare to filtered and fresh water p- value 0.001. **CONCLUSION:** prevalence of hom-B gene most frequent as compare to Dup A and ice A genes, in the patients having dyspepsia. These genes were strongly associated with bad life style and bad sewerage system along with some poor dietary habits.

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INTRODUCTION

H. Pylori, is a gram negative, spiral, microaerophilic bacteria, which could be observed within the mucus that covers gastric mucosa or amid gastric epithelium and mucus layer. It leads to a chronic little-intensity inflammation involving the stomach layer as well as is strongly associated with the growth of gastric as well as duodenal ulcers in addition to stomach cancer.¹ H. pylori create urease, catalase, and oxidase. It can form bio films as well as can transform from spiral to a most likely viable however non-cultural coccoid appearance, both ready to favour its existence. The coccoid might stick to epithelial cells of stomach in vitro.²

Colonization with *Helicobacter* is not an infection around as well as of itself however a stipulation correlated with numerous diseases of the upper GI-tract.³ Examination for *Helicobacter* is suggested in case of PUD, indolent gastric MALT lymphoma, following gastrointestinal EMR of initial stomach cancer, in case of 1st degree relative with stomach cancer, as well as in some dyspepsia cases,⁵ not regularly.⁴ Numerous means of testing are present. *Helicobacter* can be noninvasively tested through a stool antigen test, antibody test, or through urea breath test (during which the patient intakes⁶ C- or⁷ C- marked urea, which is metabolized by the bacterium, generating labeled CO₂, which can be noticed via the breath).⁵ Though, the most stable technique to detect *Helicobacter* contamination is a biopsy test while endoscopy through a CLO test, histological investigation, as well as microbial culture. Urine ELISA test is also available with 79% specificity & 96% sensitivity.⁵ No testing technique is fully failsafe. Yet biopsy relies upon the position of biopsy. Antibody test, e.g., varies between 76% to 84% sensitivity. Certain medications can influence *Helicobacter* urease function as well as provide false negatives through the urea-centered tests.⁷ Increasing antibiotic resistance escalates the requirement for a avoidance approach for the bacterium.¹⁴ Wide vaccine surveys in rodent models have exhibited promising outcomes.⁹ Numerous diets can possibly be helpful to avoid colonization with *Helicobacter* together with: red wine, green tea, Garlic, Broccoli sprouts, probiotics as well as flavonoids.¹⁰

Nutrition founded on optimum diet exhibits that genetic sensitivity to *Helicobacter pylori* could be altered as well as an escalating scientific evidence exhibits that such a nutritional regimen not just relief to avoid acquirement of the bacterium however also guards from infections effects among the individuals. Diets to be escaped in any *Helicobacter Pylori* are those carbohydrates that can be utilized via the bacteria are dairy products, coffee, chocolate, processed and red meat, refined grains, pickled products, spirits and salt.¹¹ The advantages of the lactobacilli probiotics family have as well been established through investigation. Studies exhibit likely advantages from FOS, the diet for these advantageous bacteria too.¹¹ Numerous strains of lactobacillus -salivarius & -acidophilus prevent the development of H. pylori in rats, possibly via the formation of lactic acid, even though they as well intervene with *Helicobacter* 'capability to adhere to cells. The same survey exhibited that also eradicating prevailing colonies of *Helicobacter*, the occurrence of lactobacilli prohibited colonization of bacteria.¹⁹ Diets to be escaped in any *Helicobacter Pylori* are those carbohydrates that can be utilized via the bacteria have all been numerously correlated in several research papers having higher prevalence of, or infection caused by H. Pylori.¹²

Helicobacter is transmissible, even though the particular course of conduction is mysterious.¹³ Person-to-person communication via either the fecal-oral or oral-oral course is almost certainly.¹⁴ Reliable with these conduction courses, the bacterium has been segregated from dental plaque, saliva and faces of a few contaminated individuals.¹⁵ Transmission takes place mostly within relatives in developed countries however can as well be gotten from the public in under developed nations.¹⁶ H. pylori can possibly as well be conducted orally through fecal substance by intake of waste-infected water, therefore a hygienic atmosphere could assist in the reduction of H. Pylori contamination risk.¹⁶

The incidence of H. pylori differs among various nations as well as is considerably greater in under developed as contrasted to developed nations. Most of the contaminated individuals remain asymptomatic, however almost 10-15% acquire peptic ulcer disorder. Furthermore *Helicobacter* has as well been correlated with the occurrence of gastric MALT lymphoma as well as gastric adenocarcinoma.^{17,18}

Presences of various *Helicobacter* genes have been correlated with occurrence of gastro duodenal disorder in *Helicobacter* contaminated populace. The dup-A gene of H. pylori has been correlated with duodenal ulcer as well as stomach cancer progression in some populaces. As per a multicenter study, the incidence of dup A in segregates from Chinese functional dyspeptic cases was 28.9% , Indian cases 7.1% , and Australian 38.0%,^{19,20} however correlation with stomach cancer and duodenal ulcer in Chinese cases was 62.0% in addition to 54.0% respectively.²¹ A significant correlation of dup-A gene is observed in north Indian populace however in Iranian populace it exhibited no correlation with gastro duodenal disorder.²²

Hom-B could be believed a co-indicator of *Helicobacter* strains correlated with PUD in 61.0% patients of western populace as well as 90.0% patients of East Asian populace. It is projected to be concerned in the inflammatory reaction as well as *Helicobacter* adherence, representing a fresh putative virulence factor. One more lately projected putative virulence factor is ice A that is stimulated by interaction with gastroduodenal epithelium.²³

In Pakistan 2 gastroduodenal disorders, stomach cancer and peptic ulcers are commonest issues. Genes for example hom-B, ice A & dup-A of *Helicobacter* have been correlated with phenotypic manifestation of virulence form various geographical areas worldwide. But, study like this one is not accessible from Pakistan, Thus, the study aims was detecting the existence of hom B, ice A & dup A, in Pakistani *Helicobacter* segregated from numerous people with various gastro-duodenal disorders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional analytical study was conducted at gastroenterology Department, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore and molecular techniques were performed in Centre of Excellence and Molecular Biology, University of Punjab, Lahore, with duration of two years. Ethical approval was taken from ethical review board of Shaikh Zayed Medical Complex, Lahore. All the cases with symptomatic dyspeptic patients either gender and with age more than 18 years were included in the study. All the cases having failure to detect H. Pylori by rapid urease test, portal hypertension and undergone any therapy for H. Pylori eradication in previous 4 weeks were excluded. Informed consents were obtained. Patients with dyspeptic symptoms were subjected to endoscopic examination. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy was carried out and specimens were obtained for the gastric biopsy. Specimens were inoculated in the CLO or rapid urease test gel and rest were stored in eppendorf tubes containing normal saline at -20C until DNA extraction.

DETECTION OF H. PYLORI

1. Rapid urease test

Biopsy specimens were carried out by sterile needle into solid urea agar and then at room temperature were incubated. Up to 24 hours after inoculation results were noted. If urease enzyme found in specimen, in the subsequent degeneration of urea causes the pH to rise and gel changes yellow to pink

2. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

DNA was extracted of the H-pylori by using Genra DNA extraction Kit (Life Technologies, USA) according to instructions given in protocol of the kit for Qualitative PCR detection of DNA of H. Pylori.

Primer designing and PCR protocol optimization for dup A, ice A and hom B gene:

The PCT primers sets were designed for the specific detection of dup A, ice A and hom B gene of H. Pylori using primer 3 software.

Specific Detection of dup A, ice A and hom B genes:

The designed PCR primer sets specific for the H. Pylori dup A, ice A and hom B genes were used for PCR amplification. PCR was performed for the amplification of dup A, ice A and hom B genes. The desired genes were quantified using Real-time PCR. The PCR bands of the amplified genes were gel eluted and were stored at minus 20 degree C till to be used for sequence analysis.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data will be analyzed by using SPSS version 17.0. Age was computed as Mean $\pm$ S.D, and gender with frequency and percentage. Frequencies of genotype were described by using percentage. Genotypes association of dup A, ice A and hom B with gastro duodenal diseases was presented through chi-square test. Results were considered significant if- value is ≤ 0.05 .

RESULTS

Mean age of the cases was found 41.22 ± 8.04 years, with the range of minimum 25 years and maximum 60 years. According to our study male were more affected 118(60.2%) as compare to female 78(39.8%). TABLE:1

Epigastric discomfort was found in the 196(100%)of the cases where as Bloating and Belching cases were noted as 180(91.8%) while Nausea & vomiting cases as observed as 138(70.4%). TABLE:1

The life style distribution exhibited that Hand wash 188(95.9%)was observed most frequent in all cases and exercise 36(18.4%) of cases, however municipality source water was more common following by Fresh water 48(24.5%) and Filtered water as 4(2.0%) of cases. Similarly municipality sewerage 150(81.6%) was prominent with while septic tanks in 32(16.3%) and open drain sewerage was in 4(2.0%) of cases. TABLE:1

As indicated by this study CLO/rapid urease test as well as Polymerase chain reaction quantity was noticeably 100% positive in all cases. Table.2

As per H.pylori genes distribution Hom B was the most common 76(38.8%) following by Dup A and Ice A with percentage of 56(28.6%) and 48(24.5%) respectively. Table.6

A significant association was found in the gene distribution of the H. pylori among both genders male were more linked to Dup A, while female were mostly associated with Ice A and Hom A genes, P-value 0.001 results shows in Table.3.

Significant correlations was found in H pylori genes and dyspeptic symptoms as Epigastric discomfort /pain, Bloating, Belching and Nausea/Vomit P values 0.001, 0.036, 0.012 and 0.001 respectively. Results show in Table.4.

Different type of diets is significantly associated with h pylori genes P value 0.001. Results show in table 5.

According to the life style water bad soureses were highly associated with h pylori genes as genes were mostly found in municipality water as compare to filtered and fresh water p- value 0.001. Similarly bad services of the sewerage were also highly linked with genes of h pylori as majority of genes were found in municipality sewerage as compare to septic tanks and open drains P – value 0.001 Table.6.

Table.1 Basic characteristics of the patients N=196.

Age distribution of the patients	
Age	
Mean±SD	41.22±8.04 years
Gender	
Female	78(39.8%)
Male	118(60.2%)
Dyspeptic Symptoms	
Epigastric discomfort	196(100%)
Bloating	180(91.8%)
Belching	180(91.8%)
Nausea/vomiting	138(70.4%)
Food aggravating H. Pylori	
Papper	196(100%)
cinnamon	196(100%)
Mustard	196(100%)
Nutmeg	180(91.8%)
Tomato	184 (93.9%)
Cabbage	196(100%)
Life style	
Hand wash	188(95.9%)
Exercise	36(18.4%)
Source water	
Municipality	144(73.5%)
Filtered	4(2.0%)
Fresh	48(24.5%)
Sewerage	
Municipality	150(81.6%)
Septic Tanks	32(16.3%)
Open Drains	4(2.0%)

Table.2 Cases distribution according to detection of H.pylori in gastric biopsies specimen N=196.

Biopsies	Frequency /percent
CLO/rapid urease test	
Positive	196(100%)
Negative	00(00%)
Polymerase chain reaction quantity	
Positive	196(100%)
Negative	00(00%)

Table.3 Cases distribution according to detection of H.pylori genes N=196.

H.pylori genes	Frequency /percent
Dup A	
Positive	56(28.6%)
Negative	00(00%)
Ice A	
Positive	48(24.5%)
Negative	00(00%)
Hom B	
Positive	76(38.8%)
Negative	00(00%)

Table.3 Gender distribution according to genes of H pylori N=196.

Gender distribution according to genes of H pylori							
Gender	Genes of H pylori						p-value
	Negative	dup	ice	hom	dup+hom	ice+hom	
Female	12	4	28	31	0	3	0.001
Male	23	46	10	26	7	6	
Total	35	50	38	57	7	9	

Table.4. Genes distribution of H pylori according to dyspeptic symptoms n=196.

genes distribution of H pylori according to dyspeptic symptoms							
dyspeptic symptoms	Genes of H pylori						p-value
	Negative	dup	ice	hom	dup+hom	ice+hom	
Epigastric discomfort /pain	35	50	38	57	7	9	0.001
Bloating	35	46	38	57	7	9	0.036
Belching	35	42	38	49	7	9	0.012
Nausea/Vomit	16	33	35	42	3	9	0.001

Table.5. Genes distribution of H pylori according to diet n=196.

genes distribution of H pylori according to diet							
Diet	Genes of H pylori						p-value
	Negative	dup	ice	hom	dup+hom	ice+hom	
Foods aggravating							
Nutmeg	35	42	35	52	7	9	0.02
Tomato	35	46	35	52	7	9	0.47
Foods suppressing							
vegetables	23	26	34	26	7	6	0.001
Fruits	31	30	34	46	7	6	0.004
soyabean curd	27	46	37	49	7	6	0.027
Broccoli	27	50	37	49	7	6	0.001
Olive Oil	27	42	34	48	7	6	0.37

Table.6. Genes distribution of H pylori according to life style n=196.

genes distribution of H pylori according to life style							
	Genes of H pylori						p-value
	Negative	dup	ice	hom	dup+hom	ice+hom	
SOURCE WATER							
Municipality filtered	27	46	25	33	7	6	0.001
Fresh	0	4	0	0	0	0	
	8	0	13	24	0	3	
SEWERAGE							
Municipality	31	50	25	41	7	6	0.001
Septic Tanks	4	0	12	16	0	0	
Open Drains	0	0	1	0	0	3	

DISCUSSION

Clinical progress of infection of the *H. pylori* is influenced through interaction of numerous factors of bacteria and the host. In previous studies it is reported that in factors of the microorganism, there are indications of the contribution of certain *H. pylori* genotypes in more extreme pathologies.²⁴ In this study we determined the genotyping Hom B, Dup A and Ice A is strongly associated to Epigastric discomfort/pain, Bloating, Belching and Nausea/Vomit P value 0.001. Along with strong association found with genders and life style services and diet.

In this study as per *H. pylori* genes distribution Hom B was the most common 76(38.8%) followed by Dup A and Ice A with percentage of 56(28.6%) and 48(24.5%) respectively. While in other studies As in previous investigations,²⁵ *cagA* gene most common in 71%, a finding reported by Citty et al.²⁶ it is 63.7% of the isolates and Quiroga et al.²⁷ mentioned 72.9%, Citty et al.²⁶ and Quiroga et al.²⁷ reported *cagA* gene, most common in Brazil 67%, Oliveira et al.²⁸ reported occurrence of *cagA* 79.8%, in Cuba it is reported 70.7%.^{28,29} By one more study, the incidence of hom-B gene was significantly greater in strains segregated from stomach cancer cases as contrasted to those of duodenal ulcer cases.³⁰ As per a study held in England exhibited incidence of ice-A in England segregated with ice-A₁ allele was projected 57.0% in addition to ice-A₂ allele among 36.0% of patients.

In our study IceA was found 48(24.5%). Similarly in other studies³¹ reported that the 87.4% patients were with *iceA2* positive in the contrast 12.6% patients having positive *iceA*. Other studies reported that *iceA* expression is linked to big activity of gastritis: a presentation which elevates the evidence of ulcer and gastric carcinoma.^{32,33} Studies of US and Netherlands shows the link between *iceA* and ulcer disease.^{34,35} In the consequences of this study and the discussion with respect to the *iceA*, hom A propose a high likelihood of Epigastric inconvenience/pain and bloating advancement, however considering that the patients concentrated on demonstrated non atrophic incessant gastritis and that different works recommend that this hereditary variation ought not be prevailing, the investigation of such affiliations and the appraisal of this quality as a potential pathology marker ought to gain significance.

In this study Dup A gene was additionally high prevalent, it was beforehand exhibited that homB and homA can be available in a solitary or two-duplicate frame inside a genome.³⁶ In a study, the homB/homA genes number was resolved for every one of the 372 strains conveying hom-B or hom-A only.³⁷ All of the East Asian strains conveyed the single-duplicate genotype, and this genotype was likewise the most regularly found in strains confined in Portugal (60%), France (, 69.7%), Sweden (81.8%), Germany (78.9%) and Colombia (61.1%). While very short data regarding Dup A and hom A genes is available in the literature, therefore more such studies are needed to evaluate the fine prevalence the Dup A, Ice A and hom A genes and their involvement in gastrointestinal disease.

CONCLUSION

We concluded that prevalence of hom-B gene most frequent as compare to Dup A and ice A genes, that were also high prevalent, in patients having dyspepsia. These genes were strongly associated with bad life style and bad sewerage system along with some dietary habits.

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